

A Study on a Class of MRAC Algorithms

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Abstract

A class of model reference adaptive control (MRAC) algorithms is investigated which has the special property that the Lyapunov function (and its associated time derivative) describing convergence are quadratic functions of both the position tracking error and the parameter estimation error. A nonlinear equation describing the class of algorithms that provide this type of adaptation is derived. One possible solution to this nonlinear equation is proposed which is stable and produces consistent parameter estimates.

1 Introduction

Studies in Model Reference Adaptive Control are still highly popular today even when Astrom [1] has reported, 15 years ago, over 1,500 papers on the topic at that time with hundreds of experiments conducted. This paper will address a specific class of model reference adaptive control algorithms which have the very interesting property in that both the Lyapunov function (and its time derivative along the motion trajectory) are both quadratically dependent on the tracking error and parameter estimation error. To introduce the problem of interest considered here, a brief description of the conventional method to approach this problem is first presented.

2 A Standard MRAC Problem

Figure (1) illustrates the MRAC problem (direct method) of interest here [2]. The scalar error $e_0 = y_p - y_m$ represents the tracking variable of interest between the actual plant output y_p and the reference model y_m . The unknown $m \times 1$

parameter vector θ and its adjustment mechanism require knowledge of $y_p(t)$ and $e_0(t)$. We introduce, without proof [3], Lemma (1), as a standard solution to the MRAC problem.

Lemma 1

Let a state-space description ($x \in R^n$, $e_0 \in R^1$, $v \in R^m$, $\theta \in R^m$) of Figure (1) be of the form:

$$\dot{x} = A x + b [k \theta^T v(t)] \quad (1)$$

$$e_0 = c^T x \quad (2)$$

The remaining matrices are of appropriate dimensions with A being Hurwitz, the scalar k is unknown (except for sign), the pair (A, b) is completely controllable with b known, and $v(t)$ is a measurable variable to be defined in the sequel.

For the parameter vector, θ^* represents the true value, $\hat{\theta}$ is the estimate, and $\tilde{\theta} = \hat{\theta} - \theta^*$ is the parameter error. With some abuse of notation (mixing both the Laplace transform variable p with the time domain variables), the error vector resulting from equation (2) admits to the form:

$$e_0(t) = H(p) [k \theta^T v(t)] \quad (3)$$

The transfer function $H(p)$ is strictly positive real (SPR) (of relative degree no greater than unity). The adaptation law is given by:

$$\dot{\tilde{\theta}}(t) = -\text{sgn}(k) \gamma e_0(t) v(t) \quad (4)$$

where $\gamma > 0$. $e_0(t)$ and $\theta(t)$ are globally bounded and if $v(t)$ is bounded, then $e_0(t) \rightarrow 0$, as $t \rightarrow \infty$. Associated with this problem is a Lyapunov function ($\Psi = (x, \tilde{\theta})$):

$$V(\Psi) = V(x, \tilde{\theta}) = x^T P x + \frac{|k|}{\gamma} \theta^T \tilde{\theta} \quad (5)$$

and $\gamma > 0$ controls the rate of parameter adaptation such that the parameters change more slowly

than the effects they induce on the error vector $e_0(t)$. It can be shown that:

(i) As $|\Psi| \rightarrow \infty$, $\lim V(\Psi) \rightarrow \infty$ (radial unbounded condition).

(ii) $V(\Psi) > 0$ if $\Psi \neq 0$ (positive definite property).

(iii) To show that $\dot{V}(\Psi) < 0 \forall \Psi \neq 0$ (negative definite property of \dot{V}), if A is Hurwitz, using the Kalman-Yakubovich lemma (there exist positive definite matrices P and Q such that $A^T P + P A = -Q$ and $P b = c$) and with the fact that $H(p)$ is SPR, then it follows:

$$\dot{V} = -x^T Q x < 0 \quad (6)$$

It is noted that only $e_0(t) \rightarrow 0$ as $t \rightarrow \infty$ is guaranteed and the requirement that $\hat{\theta} \rightarrow 0$ may not occur due to the fact that \dot{V} does not depend explicitly on $\hat{\theta}$. The persistent excitation condition can help alleviate this situation.

2.1 The Persistent Excitation Condition

If the stable reference model in Figure 1 satisfies:

$$\ddot{y}_m + \lambda_1 \dot{y}_m + \lambda_2 y_m = \lambda_2 r(t) \quad (7)$$

where $r(t)$ is the input forcing function to the reference model. The persistent excitation condition would normally require, on $\bar{v} = [r, e_0]^T$, through the choice of $r(t)$ in equation (7):

$$\int_t^{t+T} \bar{v} \bar{v}^T d\tau \geq \alpha_1 I \quad (8)$$

where $\exists \alpha_1 > 0$, I is the identity matrix, and $T > 0$ for any $t > 0$. With this condition in place, the biased parameter estimation problem can be mitigated. We wish now to study an alternative approach to this problem.

3 Derivation of a MRAC Algorithm with both V and \dot{V} Dependence on Parameter Estimation Error

Define a sliding state variable:

$$s := \dot{\tilde{x}} + \lambda \tilde{x} \quad (9)$$

where the term:

$$\tilde{x} = x(t) - x_m(t) = y_p - y_m \quad (10)$$

will now be used to represent tracking error. It is now convenient to represent the parameter error vector via:

$$\tilde{m} = \hat{m} - m \quad (11)$$

where m is the true parameter vector and \hat{m} is the estimate of this parameter. The appendix presents a scalar example [3] which illustrates this well known problem with examples that converge with and without biased parameter estimation error. For this paper, the main result will be presented in terms of a scalar example consistent with the notation in the appendix.

4 Main Result - The Adaptation Algorithm

The goal is to develop an algorithm to update the parameter estimator ($\hat{m}(t)$) with time update constrained by measured position signals:

$$\dot{\hat{m}} = f(\text{position measured variables}) \quad (12)$$

with no dependence or knowledge of \tilde{m} or value of the true parameter on the right hand side of equation (12). This can be realized if the following Lyapunov function is minimized:

$$V_1 = \frac{1}{2} m s^2 + \frac{1}{2} \gamma_1 \tilde{m}^2 + \frac{1}{2} \gamma_2 \dot{\tilde{m}}^2 \quad (13)$$

where s is the tracking error variable of equation (9) and the positive constants γ_1 and γ_2 will be specified in the sequel. The time derivative of V_1 along its motion trajectory is required to be specified via:

$$\dot{V}_1 = -\lambda m s^2 - \frac{1}{2} \gamma_3 \tilde{m}^2 - \frac{1}{2} \gamma_4 \dot{\tilde{m}}^2 \quad (14)$$

where λ will be defined in the sequel along with the positive constants γ_3 and γ_4 . The following assumptions are made:

Assumptions:

1. The true parameter vector m remains constant.
2. As shown in the Appendix, the following relationship is satisfied by $s(t)$ (obtained physically via (9)):

$$m \dot{s} = -\lambda m s + \tilde{m} v(t) \quad (15)$$

where the measured position variable $v(t)$ is specified via:

$$v(t) = \ddot{x}_m - 2\lambda \dot{\tilde{x}} - \lambda^2 \tilde{x} \quad (16)$$

thus measurement of $\ddot{x}_m, \dot{x}_m, x_m$ with the variables \tilde{x} and $\dot{\tilde{x}}$ are required for $s(t)$ via (9). The derivation of the algorithm is now presented.

Derivation of The Algorithm

In an effort to simultaneously satisfy equations (13) and (14), the time derivative of V_1 is first computed:

$$\dot{V}_1 = m s \dot{s} + \gamma_1 \tilde{m} \dot{\tilde{m}} + \gamma_2 \dot{\tilde{m}} \ddot{\tilde{m}} \quad (17)$$

But from equation (15):

$$m \dot{s} = -\lambda m s + \tilde{m} v(t) \quad (18)$$

Thus:

$$\dot{V}_1 = s [-\lambda m s + \tilde{m} v(t)] + \gamma_1 \tilde{m} \dot{\tilde{m}} + \gamma_2 \dot{\tilde{m}} \ddot{\tilde{m}} \quad (19)$$

but this has to match \dot{V}_1 in equation (14). This is satisfied if the following relationship holds:

$$\tilde{m} v(t) s(t) + \gamma_1 \tilde{m} \dot{\tilde{m}} + \gamma_2 \dot{\tilde{m}} \ddot{\tilde{m}} = -\frac{1}{2} \gamma_3 \tilde{m}^2 - \gamma_4 \dot{\tilde{m}}^2 \quad (20)$$

For notation simplicity, we define $\Delta(t) = v(t)s(t)$ and let $Z = \tilde{m}$. It is required to satisfy the following nonlinear differential equation in Z in order to find such a desired adaptation law:

$$\ddot{Z} \dot{Z} \gamma_2 + \dot{Z} Z \gamma_1 + \frac{1}{2} \gamma_4 \dot{Z}^2 = Z [-\Delta - \frac{1}{2} \gamma_3 Z] \quad (21)$$

The solution of the problem is still very difficult. It is desired to find a solution $Z(t) = \tilde{m} = \hat{m} - m$ to be somehow independent of m and only dependent on \hat{m} . We present here one possible solution to this problem.

A Possible Solution to the problem:

Assume a special case of the right hand side of equation (21) set to zero. This now requires the solution of:

$$Z [-\Delta - \frac{1}{2} \gamma_3 Z] = 0 \quad (22)$$

which would be satisfied by (sufficient condition):

$$[-\Delta - \frac{1}{2} \gamma_3 Z] = 0 \quad (23)$$

and can be realized via:

$$Z(t) = \tilde{m} = \frac{-2\Delta}{\gamma_3} \quad (24)$$

which is not helpful at this point because the right hand side of equation (24) implicitly depends on the unknown parameter m . The remaining equation that simultaneously must be satisfied requires:

$$\ddot{Z} \gamma_2 + \frac{1}{2} \gamma_4 \dot{Z} + Z \gamma_1 = 0 \quad (25)$$

which is still difficult to deal with since it is not desired to find Z but rather to determine \hat{m} .

However, by now using the relationship in equation (24), the following result can be derived:

$$\ddot{Z} \gamma_2 + \frac{1}{2} \gamma_4 \dot{Z} = \frac{\gamma_1}{\gamma_3} [2\Delta(t)] \quad (26)$$

and a state variable x_4 can now be defined via:

$$x_4 := \dot{Z} = \dot{\tilde{m}} = \dot{\hat{m}} \quad (27)$$

with first order state equation:

$$\dot{x}_4 = -\frac{1}{2} \frac{\gamma_4}{\gamma_2} x_4 + \frac{\gamma_1}{\gamma_2 \gamma_3} [2\Delta(t)] \quad (28)$$

It is noted the initial conditions selected are $\hat{m} = \tilde{m} = 0$, hence $x_4(0) = 0$ and equation (28) is easily integrated forward. Once $x_4(t)$ is known, then $\hat{m}(t)$ is updated via:

$$\dot{\hat{m}} = x_4(t) \quad (29)$$

and the right hand side of equation (29) requires no knowledge of m and is forced only by position measured variables $v(t)$ and $s(t)$. Presently, numerical solutions of this algorithm are ongoing with comparisons being made to some of the traditional methods. The interested reader is referred to the appendix or [2] for steps that may appear to be missing.

5 Conclusions and Discussion

A modified MRAC algorithm is proposed which gives rise to a \dot{V} expression depending on quadratic forms of both the tracking error and the parameter estimation error. A nonlinear differential equation is derived which describes potential algorithms. A special case of the solution of the derived nonlinear equation is proposed.

6 References

- [1] K. J. Astrom, "Theory and Applications of Adaptive Control - A Survey," *Automatica*, Vol. 19, No. 5, pp. 471-486, 1983.
- [2] S. Sastry and M. Bodson, "Adaptive Control - Stability, Convergence, and Robustness," Prentice Hall, 1989.
- [3] J-J. E. Slotine and W. Li, *Applied Nonlinear Control*, Prentice-Hall Inc., 1991.

7 Appendix - Application to a Problem Ill-Posed in the Sense of Not Being Persistently Exciting

For simplicity [3], the first problem of interest involves the estimation of a mass on a frictionless surface which has dynamics (m^* is the true value of the parameter):

$$m^* \ddot{x} = u \quad (30)$$

where u is the affine control variable. The reference model satisfies ($\lambda_1 > 0$, $\lambda_2 > 0$):

$$\ddot{x}_m + \lambda_1 \dot{x}_m + \lambda_2 x_m = \lambda_2 r(t) \quad (31)$$

where $r(t)$ is the input forcing function to the reference model.

To continue with this problem, a control law is chosen as:

$$u = \hat{m} (\ddot{x}_m - 2\lambda \dot{\tilde{x}} - \lambda^2 \tilde{x}) \quad (32)$$

and $\tilde{m} = \hat{m} - m^*$ represents the parameter estimation error with $\tilde{x} = x(t) - x_m(t)$ denoting the tracking error and $\lambda > 0$ is still arbitrary. A tracking error variable s is now defined via:

$$s := \dot{\tilde{x}} + \lambda \tilde{x} \quad (33)$$

It can be shown that:

$$m^* \dot{s} + \lambda m^* s = \tilde{m} v \quad (34)$$

where the $v(t)$ function (referenced previously in equation (16)) is now given by:

$$v(t) = \ddot{x}_m - 2\lambda \dot{\tilde{x}} - \lambda^2 \tilde{x} \quad (35)$$

Since m^* is constant, the adaptation law is:

$$\dot{\hat{m}} = \dot{\tilde{m}} = -\gamma v(t) s(t) \quad (36)$$

Associated with this scheme of parameter adaptation is the Lyapunov function:

$$V = \frac{1}{2} [m^* s^2 + \frac{1}{\gamma} \tilde{m}^2] \quad (37)$$

which has time derivative:

$$\dot{V} = -\lambda m^* s^2 \quad (38)$$

which is independent of \tilde{m} . It can be shown that both s and \tilde{m} are bounded from above, and thus $[\lim V]$ as $t \rightarrow \infty$ is bounded from above. Applying Barbalat's lemma to (38) implies as $t \rightarrow \infty$, $\dot{V} \rightarrow 0$, thus $s \rightarrow 0$. The problem is ill-posed, however, because the parameter estimates will not converge to the correct values. Figure (2) illustrates the tracking error convergence and Figure (3) depicts the parameter adaptation ($r(t) = 0$) for a simulation where $m^* = 2$, but the estimator converges to $\hat{m} = 1.33$. The other parameters selected for this simulation were $\gamma = 0.5$, $\lambda_1 = 10$, $\lambda_2 = 25$, $\lambda = 6$, $x(0) = x_m(0) = 0.5$, $\dot{x}(0) = \dot{x}_m(0) = 0$, $\ddot{x}_m(0) = \ddot{x}(0) = 0$.

If, however, the problem is reformulated with $r(t) = \sin(4t)$ in equation (31), then Figure (4) shows the resulting tracking error and Figure (5) demonstrates the proper parameter convergence. Thus the persistent excitation condition is satisfied in this latter case and the problem is no longer ill-posed. In practice it may not be possible for the reference model to have $r(t)$ induce the appropriate persistent excitation condition.

Figure (1) - The Standard MRAC Problem (direct method)

Reference Model and Plant Output - Non-Persistent Exciting Case

Mass Estimation - Non-Persistent Exciting Case

Model and Reference Model Output for $r(t) = \sin 4t$

Mass Estimation - Persistent Exciting Case

